

A Decision Support System for Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia Detection Based on Explainable Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract

The detection of acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) via deep learning (DL) has received great interest because of its high accuracy in detecting lymphoblasts without the need for handcrafted feature extraction. However, current DL models, such as convolutional neural networks and vision Transformers, are extremely complex, making them black boxes that perform classification in an obscure way. To compensate for this and increase the explainability of the decisions made by such methods, in this paper, we propose an innovative decision support system for ALL detection that is based on DL and explainable artificial intelligence (XAI). Our approach first introduces causality into the decision with a metric learning approach, enabling a decision to be made by analyzing the most similar images in the database. Second, our method integrates XAI techniques to allow even non-trained personnel to obtain an informed decision by analyzing which regions of the images are most similar and how the samples are organized in the latent space. The results on publicly available ALL databases confirm the validity of our approach in opening the black box while achieving similar or superior accuracy to that of existing approaches.

Keywords: Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL), Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI), Deep Learning (DL), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

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Figure 1: Examples of images of white blood cells (WBCs) taken from different subjects [1]: (a, b) *normal* WBCs in a healthy subject; (c, d) *lymphoblasts* in a subject affected by ALL. The images are stained via the hematoxylin and eosin technique and the WBCs are visible in purple.

1. Introduction

Acute lymphoblastic (or lymphocytic) leukemia (ALL) is a disease that affects white blood cells (WBCs) by modifying their morphology from a “normal” state to an “altered” state. WBCs with this altered morphology are called lymphoblasts (Fig. 1); they can be present in small numbers even in healthy individuals, especially in the bone marrow. However, an increased number of lymphoblasts in peripheral blood can indicate the presence of ALL [1, 2].

The traditional approach to detecting ALL is to perform manual inspection of samples of WBCs and check the presence and number of lymphoblasts in the blood. However, such inspection is time consuming and prone to errors

12 and can lead to fatigue. Moreover, the availability of an experienced pathol-
13 ogist is not always guaranteed [3]. To overcome the disadvantages of manual
14 inspection, which can be performed only by trained personnel, computer-
15 aided diagnosis (CAD) systems based on artificial intelligence (AI) have been
16 increasingly researched to help pathologists make diagnoses by performing
17 a preliminary classification of blood samples and detecting possible lym-
18 phoblasts [4]. In particular, AI-based approaches using deep learning (DL)
19 have shown remarkable accuracy in medical imaging [5, 6], digital pathology
20 [7], and ALL detection [8].

21 DL methods for ALL detection have exhibited high detection accuracy
22 on several publicly available datasets of ALL images; DL-based models such
23 as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [9] and vision Transformers (ViTs)
24 [10] have been applied. However, the extremely high number of complex
25 parameters involved in these models make them black boxes, which have the
26 drawback that the decision is often made in an obscure way [11].

27 To “open” the black box and provide information that can help humans
28 understand DL models, explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) methods have
29 been proposed in the literature, both general and application-specific [12],
30 and some of these approaches (e.g., CAM-based methods) have been rou-
31 tinely used along with accuracy measures to show the quality of the training
32 [13]. In fact, XAI techniques can produce more trustable models, impor-
33 tant to ensure fair decision and also to reduce the possibility of adversarial
34 attacks. However, no XAI method for ALL detection has considered a caus-
35 ability approach, where the classification is supported by information that
36 is useful for the expert in determining whether to trust the decision (e.g.,
37 by providing the cause of a specific classification) [11]. Moreover, no paper
38 in the literature for ALL detection has yet integrated XAI techniques into a
39 decision support system, where the outcome of the XAI approach not only
40 indicates high model generalizability but can also be effectively used to make
41 an informed decision.

42 In this paper, we propose an innovative decision support system for ALL
43 detection that is based on DL and XAI¹, with the goal of *i*) introducing
44 causability and *ii*) integrating XAI techniques to make an informed decision.
45 To introduce causability into the explanation, we first train a model via a
46 metric learning approach, which organizes the latent space by keeping sam-

¹We will release the source code upon acceptance of the paper.

47 ples in the same class close to each other and farther away from samples in
48 other classes. Second, in the test phase, for each query sample, we retrieve
49 the training images that are closer to it in the latent space and then classify
50 the query sample on the basis of the labels of the close retrieved images.
51 Therefore, we bring causability into the classification decision by associating
52 each sample with the images that are most similar to it, for which we already
53 know the label².

54 To integrate XAI techniques into the decision support system, we combine
55 CAM-based methods to highlight both which parts of the images contributed
56 to the decision and also which parts of the images make them similar to each
57 query sample. We also integrate dimensionality reduction methods in a way
58 that highlights the position of the query sample with respect to the close
59 images in the reduced latent space, providing additional causability infor-
60 mation in support of the decision. Some of the techniques proposed in this
61 work were also considered in the paper described in [10], which proposed
62 novel transfer learning algorithms based on both CNNs and the ViT to clas-
63 sify ALL samples accurately, as well as XAI techniques based on CAM and
64 dimensionality reduction. However, the authors of that study considered
65 XAI techniques only to evaluate the quality of the training and did not use
66 them to bring causability into the decision. Moreover, that study did not
67 consider any method of organizing the latent space, and classification was
68 performed in an obscure way. In contrast, in our work, we introduce metric
69 learning and integrate XAI techniques into a decision support system that
70 brings causability into the decision.

71 This work is the first method in the literature to propose a decision sup-
72 port system for ALL detection that integrates metric learning, majority vot-
73 ing, and XAI techniques to perform accurate and explainable classification
74 while bringing causability and insight into the decision to increase confidence
75 in the decision. Our goal is to provide the reasoning behind the classification
76 by aggregating the labels and showing the images obtained from the most
77 similar samples. While research on DL-based ALL detection is increasing
78 the number of methods, accuracy, and number of available datasets [14], de-
79 ployment of the proposed methods in clinical practice is still hindered by

²Colloquially speaking, our decision support system answers the classification question for an unknown sample by saying: *I classify this sample with the label ‘x’ because it is most similar to these images, which also have the label ‘x’.*

80 several factors, including limited consensus about what constitutes an ex-
81 plainable decision [15]. Hopefully, our contribution will pave the way for
82 greater acceptance of CAD systems based on DL.

83 The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents
84 the literature review. Section 3 introduces the method used to train the
85 model. Section 4 describes the decision support system used to perform
86 classification. Section 5 discusses the experimental results. Finally, Section 6
87 concludes the paper.

88 2. Related Works

89 The traditional methods for ALL detection that used AI techniques were
90 often based on a handcrafted feature extraction step followed by a shallow
91 classifier [16, 17]. While such methods rely on features that are more explain-
92 able, they are also limited by features that are fixed and chosen by nontrained
93 personnel (e.g., computer scientists rather than pathologists). To address the
94 limitations of handcrafted features, DL-based approaches are currently pre-
95 dominantly used [8] since they have the ability to automatically learn feature
96 representations [18]. This ability, in turn, reduces the need for pathologists
97 to be involved in the design process (except by labeling the samples [1]) and
98 enables higher classification accuracy, provided that sufficient training data
99 are available [10].

100 DL-based methods for ALL detection can be divided into three categories
101 on the basis of the approach used to achieve a higher classification accuracy
102 [19]: *i*) original learning procedures; *ii*) ad hoc network architectures; *iii*) DL-
103 based preprocessing.

104 Methods belonging to the first category focus on improving the training
105 algorithm to achieve a more accurate classification of ALL samples. Such ap-
106 proaches include pretraining the CNN on a larger database (e.g., ImageNet)
107 and then fine-tuning it on an ALL database to achieve higher accuracy [20–
108 23], following a standard procedure for medical imaging in the case of small
109 databases, for which training a CNN from scratch would result in overfit-
110 ting the training data and therefore a lower accuracy. [24]. Similarly, the
111 approaches described in [19, 25] perform pretraining, but this is done on a
112 histopathology database, leveraging the fact that the images are more similar
113 to those in the target domain. Additionally, by leveraging the similarity of
114 histopathology images to ALL samples, the approach presented in [10] ob-
115 tains a multitask DL model trained via cross-dataset transfer learning, which

116 considers both the source and target databases at the same time. This work
117 considers XAI techniques that are based on CAM and dimensionality reduc-
118 tion; however, the purpose is only to evaluate the quality of the training.

119 Unlike approaches that use only pretraining followed by fine tuning, the
120 method introduced in [26] considers a swarm optimization approach after the
121 pretraining step, with the goal of selecting the features that are more suitable
122 for ALL classification. In addition to considering the ALL database as having
123 a limited dimensionality, [27] describes the best approaches for dealing with
124 class imbalance, for example, when images from healthy subjects are more
125 widely available than images from subjects affected by ALL.

126 Methods belonging to the second category describe modifications of stan-
127 dard DL architectures that aim to extract more discriminant feature repre-
128 sentations from blood images. Examples include the approach presented in
129 [28], where a variation of the ResNet CNN architecture was used to capture
130 details of blood samples both at local and global scales, and the method
131 introduced in [29], where longer skip connections limit the problem of the
132 vanishing gradient and more strongly affect shallower layers in the CNN.
133 Other approaches have introduced ad hoc architectures with the main pur-
134 pose of avoiding overfitting on small-sized ALL datasets. Such methods in-
135 clude the approach described in [30], which uses Bayesian CNNs; the method
136 presented in [31], which proposes a shallow ResNet variant; and the method
137 proposed in [32], which is based on a CNN with fixed weights. Similarly,
138 other approaches have considered shallow or optimized CNN architectures
139 by focusing on computational complexity, such as the methods described in
140 [33, 34]. Finally, to increase the reliability of the prediction, several methods
141 have used architectures that can process multiple images at the same time
142 [35, 36].

143 Methods belonging to the third category use DL-based models specifically
144 designed to enhance blood images and therefore improve the classification
145 accuracy. Such approaches include that of [37], which uses a convolutional
146 layer designed specifically for blood images by performing stain deconvolu-
147 tion, and the method presented in [38], which uses a shallow CNN to tune
148 an unsharpening algorithm and increase the focus quality of the images.

149 To our knowledge, no paper in the literature has considered a metric
150 learning approach to bring causability into the decision or a decision support
151 system based on XAI for ALL detection.

Figure 2: Outline of the proposed methodology for training the model, which is used in the decision support system. The following steps are performed: *A*) multitask histopathological pre-training, in which we train the model on a histopathology database; *B*) class injection, in which we add images with no WBCs (by adding *ALL class 0*) and split the lymphoblast class (by adding *ALL class 3*); *C*) metric learning fine tuning, in which we tune the model on ALL images via metric learning.

152 3. Model Training Methodology

153 This section describes the methodology for training the model, which is
 154 used in the decision support system to perform classification. Fig. 2 shows
 155 the outline of the methodology.

156 *Step A:* We consider histopathological pretraining of the model to lever-
 157 age a larger and more general-purpose database that includes pathological
 158 images.

159 *Step B:* We perform class injection on the ALL database by including
 160 images with no WBCs at all (by adding *ALL class 0*) and splitting the
 161 images of the “lymphoblast” class into separate classes (by adding *ALL class*
 162 *3*). This is motivated by the idea that if images in the same class have distinct
 163 appearances, this hinders training.

164 *Step C:* We fine-tune the model on the ALL database with a metric
 165 learning approach, which leverages the greater separability of the classes
 166 achieved by the class injection step.

Figure 3: The multitask architecture used for performing histopathological pretraining. Instead of a single fully connected (FC) layer, we consider a multitask architecture with n_{FC} FC layers in parallel. For simplicity, we consider a CNN in this figure.

167 *3.1. Multitask Histopathological Pretraining*

168 We perform multitask histopathological pretraining in two steps. First,
 169 we take a standard model architecture (e.g., ResNet) and substitute the clas-
 170 sification layer (the last fully connected (FC) layer) with a multitask classi-
 171 fication layer consisting of n_{FC} FC layers in parallel (Fig. 3). In particular, we
 172 consider n_{FC} FC layers to create a multi-task learning structure and allow
 173 training the model using databases that contain labels with different cardi-
 174 nality. By adding multiple FC layers in parallel, it is possible to consider all
 175 labels during training, which can result in the model learning more general
 176 features and thus being more transferable [39].

177 Second, we train the resulting model on a database of histopathological
 178 images. The database consists of patches extracted from whole-slide images
 179 (WSIs), with each patch depicting different tissues of the human body, such
 180 as adipose, nervous, skeletal, or epithelial tissue. Each patch has a corre-
 181 sponding label describing which tissue is present in the patch; each patch
 182 can contain multiple tissues, and therefore, the labels are not mutually ex-
 183 clusive. In particular, the database considered in our study contains $n_{FC} = 3$
 184 different levels of labels, organized in a hierarchical way: each level describes
 185 a more precise label of the patch [40].

186 To train the model, we compute the L_j loss for the j -th FC layer, with
 187 $1 < j < 3$, by comparing the output of the FC layer with the corresponding

188 level of labeling, using a multilabel soft margin loss:

$$L_j = -\frac{1}{C} \sum_i \mathbf{w}_j[i] \mathbf{y}_j[i] \log((1 + \exp(-\mathbf{x}[i]))^{-1}) + (1 - \mathbf{y}_j[i]) \log\left(\frac{\exp(-\mathbf{x}[i])}{(1 + \exp(-\mathbf{x}[i]))}\right), \quad (1)$$

189 where \mathbf{y}_j is the label vector for the j -th level of labeling, C is the cardinality of
 190 \mathbf{y}_j , and \mathbf{w}_j is the vector of class weights. Each weight $w[i] \in \mathbf{w}_j$ corresponds
 191 to a tissue type and is computed as the inverse of the percentage of the
 192 cardinality of the tissue type to the total number of samples. Multilabel soft
 193 margin loss is chosen because the samples in the histopathological database
 194 each have multiple labels.

195 Then, we aggregate the L_j losses. When training a CNN, we also consider
 196 the L_{orth} orthogonality loss, which requires that the kernels of the CNN be
 197 as orthogonal as possible, thereby reducing redundancy [25, 41]. As a result,
 198 we obtain the $L_{pretrain}$ loss:

$$L_{pretrain} = \left(\frac{1}{3} \sum_{j=1}^3 L_j\right) + \lambda L_{orth}, \quad (2)$$

199 where $0 < \lambda < 1$ is the weight of the orthogonality loss.

200 3.2. Class Injection

201 We perform class injection in two steps. First, we inject images that do
 202 not contain any WBCs. In fact, most ALL databases have only images of
 203 “normal” WBCs (healthy cases) and “lymphoblasts” (possible ALL cases).
 204 Therefore, we complement the database by adding images with no WBCs
 205 (*ALL class 0*). Since in most images of WBCs, there are several red blood
 206 cells in the background, in this work, we consider images in which only red
 207 blood cells are visible, which are taken from WSIs of blood samples [25].

208 The injection of images in ALL class 0 forces the learning algorithm to
 209 detect the presence of normal WBCs, which enables the model to learn fea-
 210 tures that are distinctive of “normal” WBCs. In a two-class database (1: *nor-*
 211 *mal*; 2: *lymphoblasts*), without the presence of ALL class 0, a model would
 212 only need to differentiate lymphoblasts from “anything else”, and thus, it
 213 would not need to learn any discriminating features for normal WBCs. In

Figure 4: Examples of images from an ALL database captured with different magnifications or resolutions that have the same label: (a, b) first magnification; (c, d) second magnification. It is possible that the model will learn very different features for the two magnifications, even if the labels are the same. To address this problem, we perform class injection and separate the images into two different labels.

214 contrast, in our approach, the learned features for normal WBCs are impor-
 215 tant when analyzing the result via XAI methods, as they make it possible to
 216 understand what parts of the image contributed to the model classifying a
 217 WBC as “normal”.

218 Second, we inject additional classes by splitting images with the same
 219 label into different classes on the basis of the analysis of the features learned.
 220 In fact, some databases might contain images captured at different magnifi-
 221 cations or resolutions that nonetheless have the same label (Fig. 4). When
 222 a classification model is applied, the features of images captured in differ-
 223 ent ways present a distinctive bimodal distribution, with the corresponding
 224 features clustered in different positions of the latent space. To facilitate met-
 225 ric learning, we split such images into different labels and inject additional
 226 classes.

227 Fig. 5 shows an example of the t-SNE dimensionality reduction method
 228 applied to the features obtained by a trained model on an ALL database with
 229 the abovementioned issue, before and after the injection of additional classes.
 230 The figure shows that the “lymphoblast” class was originally bimodal, and
 231 injecting the additional class “lymphoblast (2)” enabled neater separation of
 232 the classes.

233 3.3. Metric Learning Fine-Tuning

234 We fine-tune the model, which is obtained after the multitask histopatho-
 235 logical pretraining described in Section 3.1, on the ALL database processed
 236 via the class injection procedure described in Section 3.2.

237 As the loss function, we consider a metric learning loss L_{metric} . In partic-

Figure 5: Example of t-SNE dimensionality reduction applied to an ALL database: (a) before the injection of an additional “lymphoblast” class and (b) after the injection. In (a), the “lymphoblast” class is bimodal. This is probably caused by images with the same label that were captured at different magnifications or resolutions. To facilitate metric learning, we split such images into different labels and inject an additional “lymphoblast” class. In (b), the result of t-SNE shows a neater separation of the classes.

238 ular, we consider the triplet margin loss³, which processes three tensors: the
 239 anchor a , the positive p , and the negative n :

$$L_{metric}(a, p, n) = \max\{d(a_i, p_i) - d(a_i, n_i) + 1, 0\}, \quad (3)$$

240 where $d = \|x_i - y_i\|_2$. The purpose of L_{metric} is to bring the values of a and
 241 p closer together while separating the values of a and n . As the values of
 242 a, p, n , we choose the outputs of the model before the last FC layer for two
 243 samples of the same class a, p and one sample of a different class n . As a
 244 consequence, L_{metric} tends to organize and cluster the latent space so that
 245 samples of the same class are closer to each other. Then, we add to L_{metric}
 246 the L_{orth} orthogonality loss and the cross-entropy loss L_{CE} to distinguish the
 247 different classes:

$$L_{CE}(x, class) = -w[i] \log \left(\frac{\exp(x[class])}{\sum_j \exp(x[j])} \right), \quad (4)$$

248 where \mathbf{w} is the vector of class weights, with each weight $w[i] \in \mathbf{w}$ computed
 249 as the inverse of the percentage of the cardinality of the class to the total

³<https://github.com/KevinMusgrave/pytorch-metric-learning>

Figure 6: Outline of the proposed decision support system. The system performs the following steps: *A)* explainable classification by majority voting on the labels of the closest training samples in the latent space. The classification introduces causability by attributing the cause of the classification to the labels of visually close images. *B)* Explainable decision support by highlighting the regions of the images that are most similar and the respective positions of the images in the latent space.

250 number of samples. As a result, we obtain the $L_{finetune}$ loss:

$$L_{finetune} = L_{metric} + \lambda L_{orth} + L_{CE}. \quad (5)$$

251 4. Decision Support System

252 This section describes the proposed decision support system, which is
 253 based on DL and XAI. Fig. 6 shows the outline of the system.

254 *Step A:* We classify the query images in an explainable way by retrieving,
 255 for each image, the training samples that are closest to it in the latent space.
 256 Then, we classify the images by majority voting on the classes of the retrieved
 257 training samples. We introduce causability by attributing the classification to

258 the fact that the query image is visually most similar to the selected training
 259 samples², where similarity is enforced by metric learning training.

260 *Step B:* We integrate XAI techniques for additional support of the decision
 261 by using CAM-based methods to highlight both which regions of the images
 262 contributed to the decision and which regions are most similar to the query
 263 image. Moreover, we integrate the t-SNE dimensionality reduction technique
 264 to highlight the position of the query image with respect to the images close
 265 to it in the latent space.

266 4.1. Explainable Classification: Introducing Causability

267 First, we remove the FC layer from the model and compute the feature
 268 vector \mathbf{f}_i corresponding to the last convolutional layer for each training sample
 269 i . We also compute the feature vector \mathbf{f}_Q for the query image Q in the test
 270 dataset: $\mathbf{f}_Q = \text{model}(Q)$. We normalize the feature vectors via a min-max
 271 approach, with parameters computed on the feature vectors obtained from
 272 the training samples.

273 Second, we analyze the distances in the latent space by computing the
 274 distance of \mathbf{f}_Q from each vector in the set $\{\mathbf{f}_i\}$. We obtain the set C_Q of
 275 samples close to Q by selecting the n_{close} images with the smallest distances.

$$C_Q = \text{argmin}_i d(\mathbf{f}_Q, \{\mathbf{f}_i\}) , \quad (6)$$

276 with $|C_Q| = n_{close}$.

277 Third, we obtain the result of the classification in an explainable way by
 278 majority voting on the labels of C_Q ⁴:

$$\text{result}(C_Q) = \text{majority}\{\text{label}(C_Q)\} . \quad (7)$$

279 The causability of $\text{result}(C_Q)$ lies in the fact that the classification is depen-
 280 dent on the labels associated with the majority of the n_{close} most similar
 281 training samples.

282 Fourth, we include a visual representation of the decision process by plot-
 283 ting the query image Q and the n_{close} images in C_Q . Fig. 7 shows an example
 284 of a query image Q and the corresponding images in C_Q used to perform
 285 majority voting. In the example, we chose an image from the “lymphoblast”

⁴In our experiments, it was always possible for a clear majority of the votes to be obtained.

Figure 7: Explainable classification. The proposed visual representation with the query image Q (a) and the n_{close} images in C_Q (b). We order the images in C_Q by distance in the latent space and report the corresponding labels. This representation helps in assessing the result of the classification of Q by enabling visual examination of the images that are closer in the latent space. In the example, we chose an image from the “lymphoblast” class, which was correctly classified as such.

286 class, which was correctly classified as such. In addition, for each image,
 287 we include the distances in the latent space and the corresponding labels.
 288 This representation can help in assessing the result of the classification by
 289 enabling visual examination of the images that are closer in the latent space
 290 and the corresponding distances.

291 4.2. Explainable Decision Support

292 First, we apply the Grad-CAM [42] method to analyze which parts of the
 293 images contributed to the decision. This method takes the trained model
 294 and a query image Q as input and outputs a heatmap of the regions of Q
 295 that contributed to the result of the classification:

$$\text{heatmap}_Q = \text{Grad-CAM}(Q, \text{model}) . \quad (8)$$

296 In particular, we apply this method both to the query image Q and to the set
 297 C_Q of n_{close} samples similar to Q . Fig. 8 shows a visual representation of the
 298 application of Grad-CAM to Q and C_Q , with the images in C_Q ordered by
 299 distance in the latent space and the corresponding label reported. The figure
 300 shows which parts of the image contributed to the classification of each single
 301 image. In some cases, the model focused on regions external to the WBC,
 302 providing explainable insight into whether to trust a specific prediction.

303 Second, we apply a method to Q and C_Q that is based on Grad-CAM
 304 but is designed to highlight which regions of a probe image are most similar

Figure 8: Explainable decision support. The proposed visual representation is given for Grad-CAM applied to the query image Q (a) and to the n_{close} images in C_Q (b). In addition, we order the images in C_Q by distance in the latent space and report the corresponding labels. It is possible to observe which parts of the image contributed to the classification of each single image by the trained model: in some cases, the model also focused on regions external to the WBC, providing additional insight into whether a specific classification can be trusted.

305 to a query image [43]. The method, which we call *Metric-Grad-CAM*, takes
 306 as input the trained model, the query image Q , and a probe image P and
 307 outputs a similarity heatmap for both Q and P :

$$[\text{heatmap}_Q, \text{heatmap}_P] = \text{Metric-Grad-CAM}(Q, P, \text{model}) . \quad (9)$$

308 Fig. 9 shows a visual representation of the application of *Metric-Grad-CAM*
 309 to Q and C_Q . From the figure, it is possible to observe that the heatmaps are
 310 much more localized with respect to those in Fig. 8, showing small regions of
 311 the images that are actually similar between Q and each image in C_Q . This
 312 feature enables a much more effective and localized analysis of the images in
 313 support of the decision by focusing on small regions of the WBC that could
 314 indicate a tumoral cell⁵. In particular, the heatmaps in Fig. 9 in most cases
 315 encompass the nucleus, the cytoplasm, and the border of the cell, suggesting
 316 that it is necessary to analyze these elements to make an informed decision,
 317 in accordance with the criteria defined for analyzing lymphoblasts [44].

318 Third, we give a visual representation of the positions of Q and C_Q in
 319 the latent space by applying the t-SNE dimensionality reduction technique

⁵We strongly discourage the use of our method for diagnostic activities without the advice of a pathologist. At this stage, our method must be considered only for image processing.

Figure 9: Explainable decision support. The proposed visual representation is given for Metric-Grad-CAM applied to the query image Q (a) and to the n_{close} images in C_Q (b). In addition, we order the images in C_Q by distance in the latent space and report the corresponding labels. It is possible to observe which parts of the images are similar between Q and each image in C_Q . Moreover, the heatmaps are more localized with respect to those obtained with Grad-CAM, enabling the method to focus on small regions that could indicate a tumoral cell⁵.

320 [45] to both training and test data. We highlight in the t-SNE graph the posi-
 321 tions of Q and C_Q , which can provide additional support for the decision.
 322 The graph may show that Q and C_Q are close together in the latent space,
 323 resulting in high confidence in the classification, or that they are scattered
 324 and close to the clusters of different classes, resulting in low confidence in
 325 the classification. Fig. 10 shows the proposed visual representation, plotting
 326 both training and testing samples and highlighting the query image Q and the
 327 close images in C_Q . In particular, we plot the representations for two cases:
 328 in the first case, Q and C_Q are close together in the latent space (Fig. 10a),
 329 and the image Q is correctly classified; in the second case (Fig. 10b), Q is sig-
 330 nificantly far from C_Q , and the image is incorrectly classified. The proposed
 331 visual representation can help in assigning confidence to the classification;
 332 for example, in the second case (Fig. 10b), the fact that Q and C_Q are scat-
 333 tered and close to the clusters of other classes will result in assigning low
 334 confidence to the decision.

335 5. Experimental Results

336 This section presents the experimental results, including the databases,
 337 model and training parameters used, and the results of the proposed method-
 338 ology, both quantitative and qualitative. Finally, we present examples of the
 339 proposed decision support system.

Figure 10: Explainable decision support. The proposed visual representation is given for the t-SNE technique applied to both training and testing data. We also highlight the positions of the query image Q (*square*) and the close images in C_Q (*circles*), which can provide additional support for the decision and help assign a confidence level to the classification:

- (a) Q and C_Q are close together, and the image Q is correctly classified (*high confidence*);
- (b) Q is significantly far from C_Q , and the image is incorrectly classified (*low confidence*).

340 5.1. Databases Used

- 341 • *ADP*: To perform histopathological pretraining (Section 3.1), we con-
 342 sider the Atlas of Digital Pathology (ADP) [40]⁶, which consists of
 343 17,668 patches extracted from 100 WSIs. Each patch is individually
 344 labeled with a description of the tissues present in the patch. Each
 345 patch can contain multiple tissues; therefore, the labels are not mutu-
 346 ally exclusive. For each patch, three different labels are available, with
 347 increasing levels of precision. We consider this database since it has
 348 patch-level labeling and is one of the few general-purpose histopatho-
 349 logical databases; the images are of several different tissues, making it
 350 a viable option for pretraining a model for ALL detection [10, 19].
- 351 • *ALL-IDB2*: This database contains 260 images of WBCs, with 130
 352 images of “normal” WBCs and 130 images of potential lymphoblasts.
 353 Each image is then associated with a binary label (0: *normal*; 1: *lym-*
 354 *phoblast*) [1]. The acquisition procedure used an optical microscope and
 355 a Canon PowerShot G5 camera. The acquisitions used different mag-

⁶<https://www.dsp.utoronto.ca/projects/ADP>

356 nifications of the microscope, ranging from $300x$ to $500x$, and obtained
 357 images with sizes of $H \times W = 256 \times 256$ pixels and 24-bit color depth.
 358 The images are not segmented and are already cropped and centered
 359 on the WBCs. The cropping process is relatively straightforward when
 360 analyzing images stained via the hematoxylin and eosin technique. In
 361 such images, the WBCs are highly visible, and even inexperienced op-
 362 erators can pinpoint the center of each cell (see Fig. 1). We enhance
 363 the database by applying the unsharpening method described in [38]
 364 and performing z score normalization, transforming the images to have
 365 a mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1. The normalization parameters
 366 are computed on the training subset. We perform class injection on the
 367 ALL database as described in Section 3.2 by first adding 130 images
 368 taken from patches that do not contain any WBCs extracted from WSIs
 369 of ALL-IDB1 via the ALL-IDB Patches approach [9]. We use 130 im-
 370 ages since this is the number of images belonging to the class “normal”
 371 and to the class “lymphoblast” in the ALL-IDB2 database. Second, we
 372 split the images of the class “lymphoblast” into “lymphoblast (1)” and
 373 “lymphoblast (2)”, on the basis of their bimodal distribution, as de-
 374 scribed in Section 3.2. As a result, we obtain a database with 4 classes:
 375 (0: *nothing*; 1: *normal*; 2: *lymphoblast (1)*; 3: *lymphoblast (2)*). The
 376 class distribution is described in Table 1. Examples of images of the
 377 corresponding classes are shown in Fig. 11.

- 378 • *ALL-IDB Patches*: This dataset contains 10,260 images of WBCs ob-
 379 tained by cropping patches from WSIs via the methodology described
 380 in [9]. The patches can contain red blood cells, “normal” WBCs, or lym-
 381 phoblasts, and it is possible for a patch to contain multiple elements.
 382 To evaluate the proposed methodology on the dataset, we adjust it
 383 for single-output classification by considering only the patches associ-
 384 ated with a single class. We then apply the proposed class injection
 385 method, similar to the ALL-IDB2 dataset. As a result, we obtain a
 386 database with 4 classes: 0: *nothing*; 1: *normal*; 2: *lymphoblast (1)*;
 387 3: *lymphoblast (2)*. We enhance the database by performing z score
 388 normalization. The class distribution is described in Table 2.
- 389 • *C-NMC*: This dataset comprises 10,661 images of WBCs belonging
 390 to the classes 0: normal and 1: lymphoblasts. The images were cap-
 391 tured with a Nikon DS5M camera and labeled by an expert pathologist.

Table 1: Number of samples for each class in the ALL-IDB2 database after class injection.

Class	Label	Num. of samples
0	Nothing	130
1	Normal	130
2	Lymphoblast (1)	73
3	Lymphoblast (2)	57
-	<i>Total</i>	390

Figure 11: Examples of images from the ALL database after class injection. (a) 0: *nothing*; (b) 1: *normal*; (c) 2: *lymphoblast (1)*; (d) 3: *lymphoblast (2)*.

392 The images were then stain normalized to have uniform color, cropped
 393 around the cell, and segmented to show only the region of the WBC,
 394 resulting in images with size $H \times W = 450 \times 450$ pixels and 24 bit color
 395 depth [46]. We enhance the database by applying the unsharpening
 396 method described in [47] and performing z score normalization. The
 397 class distribution is described in Table 3.

- 398 • *PBC*: This dataset contains 17, 092 images of “normal” WBCs, captured
 399 via a CellaVision DM96; they belong to 8 classes, representing different
 400 kinds of healthy WBCs: 0: *Basophil*; 1: *Eosinophil*; 2: *Erythroblast*;
 401 3: *Immature granulocyte*; 4: *Lymphocyte*; 5: *Monocyte*; 6: *Neutrophil*;
 402 7: *Platelet*. The images are annotated by expert pathologists and have
 403 a size of $H \times W = 360 \times 363$ pixels and 24-bit color depth [48]. We
 404 enhance the database by performing z score normalization. The class
 405 distribution is described in Table 4.

406 5.2. Model and Training Parameters

407 As models, we consider both CNNs and ViT, given their successful appli-
 408 cation in several fields, including histopathological image classification and

Table 2: Number of samples for each class in the ALL-IDB `Patches` database after class injection.

Class	Label	Num. of samples
0	Nothing	6921
1	Normal	1829
2	Lymphoblast (1)	232
3	Lymphoblast (2)	336
-	<i>Total</i>	9318

Table 3: Number of samples for each class in the C-NMC database.

Class	Label	Num. of samples
0	Normal	3389
1	Lymphoblast	7272
-	<i>Total</i>	10661

409 ALL detection [19, 40, 49, 50]. In particular, we consider the most used CNN
 410 variants ResNet18, ResNet34, ResNet50, and the vit_b_16.

411 We train the models via the multitask histopathological pretraining method
 412 described in Section 3.1, which uses the parameters and learning procedure
 413 detailed in [25]. When training vit_b_16, we consider the model pretrained
 414 on the IMAGENET-21K database and fine tuned on IMAGENET-1K⁷, then
 415 apply the histopathological pretraining. Before performing the metric learn-
 416 ing fine-tuning method described in Section 3.3, we apply a warmup phase,
 417 using the ALL database, by training only the last FC layers of the model.
 418 The purpose of this warmup is to prevent gradients that are too large from
 419 initially flowing on the last FC layers since these layers are randomly ini-
 420 tialized but are preceded by convolutional layers that are pretrained on the
 421 histopathological database [39]. In particular, in the warmup phase, we apply
 422 an SGD for 2 epochs, with a learning rate of $lr_{warmup} = 0.02$, a momentum of
 423 $= 0.9$, and a weight decay of $= 5e^{-4}$. After the warmup, we perform metric
 424 learning fine-tuning by applying an SGD for 90 epochs, with a learning rate
 425 of $lr_{finetune} = 2e^{-4}$, a momentum of $= 0.9$, and a weight decay of $= 5e^{-4}$.
 426 After every 20 epochs, we reduce the learning rate by half. We consider a
 427 deep tuning approach, enabling gradient update on all layers of the model

⁷<https://github.com/lukemelas/PyTorch-Pretrained-ViT>

Table 4: Number of samples for each class in the PBC database.

Class	Label	Num. of samples
0	Basophil	1218
1	Eosinophil	3117
2	Erythroblast	1551
3	Immature granulocyte	2895
4	Lymphocyte	1214
5	Monocyte	1420
6	Neutrophil	3329
7	Platelet	2348
-	<i>Total</i>	17 092

428 [51].

429 When considering the ALL-IDB Patches, C-NMC, and PBC databases,
 430 we removed the warmup phase and the orthogonal loss L_{orth} . We experimen-
 431 tally evaluated that such operations reduce the accuracy in those databases.

432 To reduce the possibility of overfitting, we perform data augmentation
 433 during training. In particular, we only consider data augmentation tech-
 434 niques that do not distort the image pattern, such as random rotations and
 435 random horizontal/vertical flips. To avoid distorting the image pattern, we
 436 do not consider zooming or shifting.

437 We test the generalizability of the model via n -fold cross-validation, with
 438 $n = 5$. In each iteration, the training subset contains approximately 3/5 of
 439 the images, whereas the validation and testing subsets contain approximately
 440 1/5 of the images each. At the end of the training, we consider the model
 441 with the weights corresponding to the best accuracy on the validation subset.
 442 We report the final results after averaging the accuracy on the testing subset
 443 across 5 iterations.

444 We perform testing via the explainable classification step described in
 445 Section 4.1, which uses $n_{close} = 3$ neighbors for the ALL-IDB2 database and
 446 $n_{close} = 5$ for the others. We use the Euclidean distance function; however,
 447 other distance functions can be applied.

448 5.3. Results

449 5.3.1. Quantitative Evaluation

450 As an error measure, we consider the classification accuracy as the per-
 451 centage of samples that are correctly classified with respect to the total num-
 452 ber of images in the testing subset of the ALL database. As additional

Table 5: Accuracy results on the ALL-IDB2 database.

Ref.	Model	Accuracy* (%) (MeanStd)	Sensitivity*	Specificity*
[38]	ResNet18	96.00 _{1.13}	94.76 _{2.82}	97.23 _{2.02}
[19]	HistoTNet _{ResNet18}	97.23 _{1.15}	97.54 _{2.02}	96.92 _{2.43}
	HistoTNet _{ResNet34}	98.31 _{1.91}	98.15 _{3.34}	98.46 _{1.09}
[32]	ALLNet _{ResNet18}	97.85 _{0.58}	98.46 _{1.54}	97.23 _{2.01}
	ALLNet _{ResNet34}	98.46 _{0.84}	97.85 _{1.75}	99.08 _{1.38}
[9]	OrthoALLNet _{ResNet18}	98.46 _{0.97}	99.08 _{0.84}	97.85 _{2.33}
	OrthoALLNet _{ResNet34}	98.62 _{0.90}	97.85 _{2.06}	99.38_{0.84}
	ResNet18	99.74_{0.51}	100.00_{0.00}	99.26_{1.66}
	ResNet34	99.23 _{0.63}	98.57 _{1.96}	98.95 _{2.35}
	ResNet50	99.74 _{0.51}	100.00 _{0.00}	99.26 _{1.66}
	vit_b_16	98.21 _{1.46}	94.79 _{4.03}	100.00 _{0.00}

Notes: * We computed the accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity for our approach after processing the confusion matrix combining class 0: *nothing* with class 1: *normal* and combining class 2: *lymphoblast (1)* with class 3: *lymphoblast (2)*.

453 measures, we compute the specificity and sensitivity, as well as the confu-
 454 sion matrix indicating the percentages of true positives, true negatives, false
 455 positives, and false negatives, according to the specifications reported in [1].

456 Table 5 reports the error measures using the proposed methodology on
 457 the ALL-IDB2 database compared with those of recent works in the litera-
 458 ture. All the approaches listed in the table use histopathological pretraining
 459 and the same training hyperparameters. The table shows that our approach
 460 achieves superior accuracy with respect to recent works in the literature. In
 461 particular, ResNet18 and ResNet50 achieve the best result, with a classifi-
 462 cation accuracy of 99.74%. With respect to the methods in the literature,
 463 our method has the advantages of increased accuracy and an added decision
 464 support system, which increases the causability and explainability of the deci-
 465 sions. Table 6 also presents the corresponding confusion matrix, which shows
 466 that the class injection does not negatively affect the accuracy, since the only
 467 classification errors are between the “normal” WBCs and the lymphoblasts.
 468 In fact, no image of class 0: *nothing* was misclassified, and no image of class
 469 2: *lymphoblast (1)* was misclassified as class 3: *lymphoblast (2)* or vice versa.

470 Table 7, Table 8, and Table 9 present the results of the proposed method-

Table 6: Average confusion matrix of the results obtained using the ResNet18 configuration on the ALL-IDB2 database.

		Predicted			
		0: <i>nothing</i>	1: <i>normal</i>	2: <i>lymph. (1)</i>	3: <i>lymph. (2)</i>
True	0: <i>nothing</i>	33.33%	0 %	0 %	0 %
	1: <i>normal</i>	0 %	33.07%	0 %	0.25%
	2: <i>lymph. (1)</i>	0 %	0 %	18.71%	0 %
	3: <i>lymph. (2)</i>	0 %	0 %	0 %	14.64%

471 ology on the ALL-IDB Patches, C-NMC, and PBC databases, respectively.
 472 In the tables, we compare the results of our methodology with those of the
 473 approaches presented in [9], [10], and [52], which exhibit state-of-the-art accu-
 474 racy on the databases.

475 Table 7 and Table 8 show that our approach achieves a greater accuracy
 476 with respect to recent works in the literature also when applied on the ALL-
 477 IDB Patches and C-NMC databases. In particular, for ALL-IDB Patches the
 478 ResNet34 achieves the best result, with a classification accuracy of 99.20%,
 479 while for C-NMC the vit_b_16 achieves the best result with 97.32% accu-
 480 racy. It is worth noting that for ALL-IDB2 and ALL-IDB Patches we applied
 481 the class injection step, which enabled the models trained on these databases
 482 to more accurately distinguish between classes. Table 9 shows that the pro-
 483 posed methodology achieves similar results to those of the methods from
 484 the literature, with a slight decrease in accuracy caused by the use of a
 485 simpler classifier (majority voting). In particular, on the PBC database we
 486 obtain a best result of 99.00%, only 0.91% less than the current literature
 487 best (99.91%). However, the proposed method is more explainable than the
 488 methods from current literature. To increase the accuracy, it would also be
 489 possible to combine the proposed approach with different architectures and
 490 training algorithms, provided that a regularized latent space is obtained.

491 5.3.2. Qualitative Evaluation

492 To perform the qualitative evaluation, we consider the results obtained
 493 on ALL-IDB2 using the ResNet18 CNN, which obtained the highest classi-
 494 fication accuracy (see Table 5). In particular, we apply the t-SNE dimen-
 495 sionality reduction technique in the “standard configuration”; it is applied to
 496 the testing subset of the data, considering the feature space obtained after
 497 the last convolutional layer of the CNN (the same feature space used for
 498 metric learning and distance computation). This analysis is routinely per-

Table 7: Accuracy results on the ALL-IDB Patches database.

Ref.	Model	Accuracy* (%) (MeanStd)	Sensitivity*	Specificity*
[9]	OrthoALLNet _{ResNet18}	95.91 _{0.81}	–	–
	OrthoALLNet _{ResNet34}	96.06 _{0.78}	–	–
	ResNet18	99.14 _{0.18}	95.92 _{1.26}	99.35 _{0.14}
	ResNet34	99.20_{0.18}	96.01_{2.27}	99.39_{0.15}
	ResNet50	98.99 _{0.25}	94.76 _{1.38}	99.27 _{0.26}
	vit_b_16	99.13 _{0.14}	94.39 _{1.32}	99.44_{0.23}

Notes: * We computed the accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity for our approach after processing the confusion matrix combining class 0: *nothing* with class 1: *normal* and combining class 2: *lymphoblast (1)* with class 3: *lymphoblast (2)*.

Table 8: Accuracy results on the C-NMC database.

Ref.	Model	Accuracy (%) (MeanStd)	Sensitivity	Specificity
[10]	ResNet18 _{ADP,3,CNMC}	95.99 _{0.16}	90.94 _{1.33}	98.35 _{0.54}
	ViT _{ImageNet,ADP,1,CNMC}	97.10 _{0.38}	94.00 _{1.09}	98.54_{0.25}
	ResNet18	95.86 _{0.57}	97.81 _{0.40}	91.71 _{1.56}
	ResNet34	95.66 _{0.51}	97.68 _{0.52}	91.31 _{1.09}
	ResNet50	95.01 _{0.41}	97.26 _{0.17}	90.23 _{0.79}
	vit_b_16	97.32_{0.22}	99.01_{0.13}	93.67 _{0.88}

499 formed in several papers to show the effectiveness of the training [10]. Fig. 12
500 shows the results on the ALL-IDB2 database, indicating that the four classes
501 are effectively separated and that class 2: *lymphoblast (1)* and class 3: *lym-*
502 *phoblast (2)* are separated, supporting the method of separating the classes
503 during the class injection step (Section 3.2).

504 5.3.3. Ablation Study

505 To evaluate the effects of class injection and metric learning, we analyze
506 them separately by computing the accuracy with and without them on the
507 ALL-IDB2 database. We use ResNet18 since it provided the best accuracy
508 (see Table 5). Table 10 shows the obtained results. The table shows that the
509 combined use of metric learning and class injection allows us to obtain the

Table 9: Accuracy results on the PBC database.

Ref.	Model	Accuracy (%) (Mean _{Std})
[52]	Custom CNN	99.91
	ResNet18	98.95 _{0.13}
	ResNet34	98.99 _{0.25}
	ResNet50	99.00 _{0.10}
	vit_b_16	98.69 _{0.18}

Figure 12: Results of the t-SNE algorithm in the “standard configuration”, applied to the testing subset of the ALL-IDB2 database and considering the feature space obtained after the last convolutional layer of the CNN: (a) ResNet18; (b) ResNet34. In both cases, it is seen that the four classes are effectively separated and that class 2: *lymphoblast (1)* and class 3: *lymphoblast (2)* are distinct.

510 best results⁸.

511 5.3.4. Running Times

512 The hardware used in our experiments consists of a laptop computer
 513 equipped with a 12th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-12800H @2.40 GHz pro-
 514 cessor, 64 GB RAM and an Nvidia RTX A1000 GPU. The training process
 515 for the ResNet18 took between 2 m 45 s and 3 m for 90 epochs and 234 im-
 516 ages. For comparison, the training process took approximately 2 m for a

⁸Because the accuracy of the proposed methodology is almost saturated, we did not perform a sensitivity analysis for the training hyperparameters.

Table 10: Ablation study of the proposed methodology on the ALL-IDB2 database.

Model	Metric learning	Class injection	Accuracy (%) (Mean _{Std})
ResNet18			99.49 _{0.63}
		✓	99.49 _{0.63}
	✓		98.97 _{0.96}
	✓	✓	99.74_{0.51}

517 method based on a plain ResNet [19]. The inference times for both meth-
 518 ods were approximately 1 s for 78 images. We did not consider visualization
 519 since *i*) saving and visualizing plots also depends on hard drive speed and
 520 *ii*) to reduce the inference time, it would be possible to request only the
 521 visualization of a specific sample. Moreover, to evaluate the scalability of
 522 our approach in the testing phase, we tripled the size of the dataset using a
 523 dummy replication scheme, with no significant difference in inference time.
 524 Finally, we believe that further speed improvements could be achieved by
 525 considering techniques for optimizing DL models [53, 54].

526 5.4. Decision Support System

527 We evaluate the proposed decision support system by presenting exam-
 528 ples of the visual representations associated with a classification. In each
 529 representation, we include one example of a correct classification and one
 530 example of an incorrect classification.

531 First, we present the visual representation for the explainable classifica-
 532 tion, as described in Section 4.1. The representation includes the query image
 533 Q , the images C_Q close in the feature space used to perform the classification,
 534 and the distances in the feature space. Fig. 13 is the visual representation,
 535 which shows that in a correct classification, the images in C_Q are significantly
 536 more similar to those in Q than for an incorrect classification. Moreover, in
 537 the case of a correct classification, the average distance between Q and C_Q
 538 is < 1 , which is significantly lower than that of an incorrect classification,
 539 where the average distance is > 4 .

540 Second, we present the visual representation with Metric-Grad-CAM, as
 541 described in Section 4.2. Fig. 14 shows the proposed explainable decision sup-
 542 port method based on Metric-Grad-CAM. The figure shows that in the cor-
 543 rect classification, Metric-Grad-CAM highlights regions of the images in C_Q
 544 within the WBCs that are similar to those in the query image Q , in contrast

Figure 13: Decision support system on the ALL-IDB2 database: explainable classification. Examples of the visual representation of the decision process for a correct classification (a : query image Q ; b : close images C_Q) and an incorrect classification (c : query image Q ; d : close images C_Q). In the correct classification, the selected close images (b) are very similar to the query image (a). Moreover, the average distance in the feature space is < 1 . On the other hand, in the incorrect classification, the close images (d) are somewhat dissimilar to the query image (c). Moreover, the average distance in the feature space is > 4 , which is significantly greater than that of correct classification.

545 to the case of incorrect classification, where Metric-Grad-CAM highlights re-
 546 gions that are not included within the WBC and therefore are probably not
 547 significant⁵.

548 Third, we present the visual representation with the t-SNE dimensionality
 549 reduction technique applied to both the training and testing data, highlight-
 550 ing in the t-SNE graph the positions of Q and C_Q , as described in Section 4.2.
 551 Fig. 15 shows the proposed explainable decision support based on t-SNE,
 552 showing that for the correct classification, Q and C_Q are much closer than
 553 they are in the incorrect classification case.

Figure 14: Decision support system on the ALL-IDB2 database: explainable decision support. Examples of the visual representation using Metric-Grad-CAM for a correct classification (a : query image Q , b : close images C_Q) and an incorrect classification (c : query image Q , d : close images C_Q). For the correct classification, in the selected close images (b), Metric-Grad-CAM highlights regions that are within the WBCs and are similar to those in the query image (a). On the other hand, for the incorrect classification, Metric-Grad-CAM highlights regions that are not included within the WBC and therefore are probably not significant.

554 6. Conclusions

555 In this paper, we propose the first decision support system for ALL de-
 556 tection; it is based on deep learning and explainable artificial intelligence,
 557 with the purpose of providing an informed decision by introducing causabil-
 558 ity into the classification result. Our approach first trains a model via a
 559 metric learning approach, which organizes the latent spaces and brings sam-
 560 ples belonging to the same class closer to each other and farther from sam-
 561 ples of other classes. Second, the approach performs explainable classification
 562 of each white blood cell as either 0: *normal* or 1: *lymphoblast* by majority voting
 563 of the closest samples in the latent space. *Colloquially speaking, our decision*

Figure 15: Decision support system on the ALL-IDB2 database: explainable decision support. Examples of the proposed visual representation are given based on the t-SNE algorithm for correct classification (a) and incorrect classification (b). The representation includes both training and testing data and highlights the positions of the query image Q (square) and the close images C_Q (circles) in the latent space. In the correct classification case, Q and C_Q are much closer together than in the incorrect classification case.

564 *support system answers the classification question for an unknown sample by*
 565 *saying, “I classify this sample with the label ‘x’ because it is most similar to*
 566 *these images that also have the label ‘x’ ”.* The method then uses integrated
 567 XAI techniques to provide an informed decision by considering CAM-based
 568 techniques that highlight which parts of the images are most similar to the
 569 query image and a t-SNE-based dimensionality reduction method that shows
 570 the distances between the closest samples with respect to the query image
 571 and the corresponding position.

572 In addition to proposing a decision support system, the advantages of
 573 our methodology reside also in the class injection, which enabled the DL
 574 models to have a larger output space to embed the results of the classification.
 575 Combined with metric learning, the result is a more regularized latent space,
 576 which can be leveraged by a simple majority voting classifier providing an
 577 explainable decision. The results on several publicly available ALL databases
 578 demonstrate classification accuracy that is similar to or greater than that
 579 of state-of-the-art methods, at the same time introducing causability into
 580 classification while providing tools to assess the confidence of the decision.
 581 Future works will investigate the feasibility of a class injection step for other
 582 databases, as well as the transferability of the learned knowledge between

583 different datasets.

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